

Supporting Information

Prospective Life Cycle Assessment of a model Magnesium Battery*Sebastián P. Bautista², Marcel Weil^{1,2*}, Manuel Baumann¹, Claudia Tomasini²*

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Table S1: Life cycle impacts per MWh in the ‘complete utilization of batteries’ application

		LIB-NMC	LIB-LFP	VRLA	LiS	VRFB	MgS-Evo2
Cumulative energy demand [MJ]	Production	576.2	446.5	420.8	2559.2	819.6	726.9
	Use phase	430.5	908.8	2512.5	908.8	2726.3	908.8
Agricultural land occupation [m2a]	Production	2.6672	2.0160	2.7825	9.5486	1.5889	2.4029
	Use phase	0.0104	0.0220	0.0608	0.0220	0.0660	0.0220
Climate change [kg CO2-eq]	Production	35.9056	31.8354	25.9290	112.2320	55.8749	44.6317
	Use phase	24.1580	51.0002	141.0006	51.0002	153.0007	51.0002
Fossil depletion [kg oil-eq]	Production	9.7245	7.6437	7.6034	43.1478	17.8463	13.3230
	Use phase	7.3174	15.4478	42.7086	15.4478	46.3433	15.4478
Freshwater ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	1.4691	1.1966	2.0768	2.0618	1.1511	0.8767
	Use phase	1.3912	2.9369	8.1197	2.9369	8.8108	2.9369
Freshwater eutrophication [kg P-eq]	Production	0.0411	0.0444	0.0688	0.0825	0.0321	0.0288
	Use phase	0.0245	0.0518	0.1432	0.0518	0.1554	0.0518
Human toxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	62.2309	65.6757	144.6739	73.3244	115.8623	30.8278
	Use phase	17.5167	36.9797	102.2379	36.9797	110.9390	36.9797
Ionising radiation [kg U235-eq]	Production	6.6129	5.0136	2.9874	29.8696	3.1167	6.6797
	Use phase	0.6047	1.2766	3.5295	1.2766	3.8299	1.2766
Marine ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	1.4784	1.2325	2.1679	1.9665	1.2171	0.8397
	Use phase	1.2426	2.6232	7.2524	2.6232	7.8696	2.6232
Marine eutrophication [kg N-eq]	Production	0.1262	0.0310	0.0453	0.1656	0.0751	0.0376
	Use phase	0.0199	0.0421	0.1163	0.0421	0.1262	0.0421
Metal depletion [kg Fe-eq]	Production	44.8012	11.5884	74.3522	30.0402	40.0138	5.5090
	Use phase	0.9639	2.0350	5.6261	2.0350	6.1050	2.0350
Natural land transformation [m2]	Production	0.0053	0.0041	0.0061	0.0149	0.0091	0.0052
	Use phase	0.0005	0.0011	0.0032	0.0011	0.0034	0.0011
Ozone depletion [kg CFC-11-eq]	Production	0.0001	0.0002	0.0000	0.0000	0.0002	0.0000
	Use phase	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Particulate matter formation [kg PM10-eq]	Production	0.1649	0.0719	0.1167	0.2174	0.2254	0.1376
	Use phase	0.0293	0.0618	0.1708	0.0618	0.1854	0.0618
Photochemical oxidant	Production	0.1482	0.0847	0.1233	0.3185	0.2627	0.1468

formation [kg NMVOC]	Use phase	0.0393	0.0829	0.2293	0.0829	0.2488	0.0829
Terrestrial acidification [kg SO ₂ -eq]	Production	0.5708	0.1921	0.3560	0.5196	0.7061	0.1858
	Use phase	0.1376	0.2905	0.8032	0.2905	0.8715	0.2905
Terrestrial ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	0.0065	0.0058	0.0062	0.0089	0.0257	0.0033
	Use phase	0.0007	0.0016	0.0043	0.0016	0.0047	0.0016
Urban land occupation [m ² a]	Production	0.5698	0.5400	0.4831	0.8337	0.5004	0.4449
	Use phase	0.0939	0.1983	0.5482	0.1983	0.5948	0.1983
Water depletion [m ³]	Production	0.9668	1.1299	0.1857	0.7178	0.1592	0.1556
	Use phase	0.0882	0.1862	0.5147	0.1862	0.5585	0.1862
Abiotic depletion potential [kg Sb-eq]	Production	0.0319	0.0217	0.2546	0.0192	0.0038	0.0191
	Use phase	0.0008	0.0017	0.0047	0.0017	0.0051	0.0017

Table S2: Life cycle impacts per MWh in the 'photovoltaics self-consumption' application.

		LIB-NMC	LIB-LFP	VRLA	LiS	VRFB	MgS-Evo2
Cumulative energy demand [MJ]	Production	1052.5	1223.2	1064.1	2559.2	2495.0	863.0
	Use phase	275.4	581.4	1607.3	581.4	1744.1	581.4
Agricultural land occupation [m ² a]	Production	4.8716	5.5233	7.0367	9.5486	4.8370	2.8527
	Use phase	0.0011	0.0024	0.0065	0.0024	0.0071	0.0024
Climate change [kg CO ₂ -eq]	Production	65.5809	87.2204	65.5717	112.2320	170.0911	52.9874
	Use phase	4.5310	9.5654	26.4454	9.5654	28.6961	9.5654
Fossil depletion [kg oil-eq]	Production	17.7616	20.9417	19.2283	43.1478	54.3267	15.8173
	Use phase	1.3307	2.8092	7.7665	2.8092	8.4275	2.8092
Freshwater ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	2.6832	3.2783	5.2520	2.0618	3.5042	1.0408
	Use phase	0.9308	1.9651	5.4328	1.9651	5.8952	1.9651
Freshwater eutrophication [kg P-eq]	Production	0.0751	0.1215	0.1739	0.0825	0.0978	0.0342
	Use phase	0.0038	0.0081	0.0224	0.0081	0.0243	0.0081
Human toxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	113.6638	179.9333	365.8642	73.3244	352.7011	36.5993
	Use phase	6.5591	13.8469	38.2826	13.8469	41.5407	13.8469
Ionising radiation [kg U ₂₃₅ -eq]	Production	12.0783	13.7360	7.5549	29.8696	9.4877	7.9303
	Use phase	0.3914	0.8263	2.2844	0.8263	2.4789	0.8263
Marine ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	2.7003	3.3768	5.4823	1.9665	3.7050	0.9969
	Use phase	0.8286	1.7492	4.8360	1.7492	5.2476	1.7492
Marine eutrophication [kg N- eq]	Production	0.2305	0.0849	0.1145	0.1656	0.2287	0.0446
	Use phase	0.0059	0.0124	0.0342	0.0124	0.0371	0.0124
Metal depletion [kg Fe-eq]	Production	81.8286	31.7491	188.0286	30.0402	121.8075	6.5403
	Use phase	1.6569	3.4979	9.6706	3.4979	10.4937	3.4979
Natural land transformation [m ²]	Production	0.0096	0.0113	0.0154	0.0149	0.0277	0.0062
	Use phase	0.0002	0.0005	0.0013	0.0005	0.0014	0.0005
Ozone depletion [kg CFC-11-eq]	Production	0.0003	0.0006	0.0000	0.0000	0.0006	0.0000
	Use phase	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Particulate matter formation [kg PM ₁₀ -eq]	Production	0.3012	0.1971	0.2952	0.2174	0.6861	0.1634
	Use phase	0.0108	0.0228	0.0630	0.0228	0.0684	0.0228
Photochemical oxidant formation [kg NMVOC]	Production	0.2706	0.2320	0.3119	0.3185	0.7998	0.1743
	Use phase	0.0169	0.0356	0.0985	0.0356	0.1069	0.0356
Terrestrial acidification [kg SO ₂ -eq]	Production	1.0426	0.5262	0.9003	0.5196	2.1496	0.2206
	Use phase	0.0256	0.0541	0.1496	0.0541	0.1623	0.0541

Terrestrial ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	0.0119	0.0158	0.0158	0.0089	0.0783	0.0039
	Use phase	0.0007	0.0015	0.0040	0.0015	0.0044	0.0015
Urban land occupation [m2a]	Production	1.0408	1.4794	1.2216	0.8337	1.5233	0.5282
	Use phase	0.0394	0.0832	0.2300	0.0832	0.2496	0.0832
Water depletion [m3]	Production	1.7659	3.0957	0.4696	0.7178	0.4847	0.1848
	Use phase	0.0218	0.0460	0.1271	0.0460	0.1379	0.0460
Abiotic depletion potential [kg Sb-eq]	Production	0.0583	0.0593	0.6438	0.0192	0.0117	0.0226
	Use phase	0.0031	0.0066	0.0183	0.0066	0.0198	0.0066

Table S3: Life cycle impacts per MWh in the 'energy management' application.

		LIB-NMC	LIB-LFP	VRLA	LiS	VRFB	MgS-Evo2
Cumulative energy demand [MJ]	Production	576.2	446.5	1154.1	2559.2	819.6	726.9
	Use phase	430.5	908.8	2512.5	908.8	2726.3	908.8
Agricultural land occupation [m2a]	Production	2.6672	2.0160	7.6323	9.5486	1.5889	2.4029
	Use phase	0.0104	0.0220	0.0608	0.0220	0.0660	0.0220
Climate change [kg CO2-eq]	Production	35.9056	31.8354	71.1225	112.2320	55.8749	44.6317
	Use phase	24.1580	51.0002	141.0006	51.0002	153.0007	51.0002
Fossil depletion [kg oil-eq]	Production	9.7245	7.6437	20.8560	43.1478	17.8463	13.3230
	Use phase	7.3174	15.4478	42.7086	15.4478	46.3433	15.4478
Freshwater ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	1.4691	1.1966	5.6966	2.0618	1.1511	0.8767
	Use phase	1.3912	2.9369	8.1197	2.9369	8.8108	2.9369
Freshwater eutrophication [kg P-eq]	Production	0.0411	0.0444	0.1886	0.0825	0.0321	0.0288
	Use phase	0.0245	0.0518	0.1432	0.0518	0.1554	0.0518
Human toxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	62.2309	65.6757	396.8355	73.3244	115.8623	30.8278
	Use phase	17.5167	36.9797	102.2379	36.9797	110.9390	36.9797
Ionising radiation [kg U235-eq]	Production	6.6129	5.0136	8.1944	29.8696	3.1167	6.6797
	Use phase	0.6047	1.2766	3.5295	1.2766	3.8299	1.2766
Marine ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	1.4784	1.2325	5.9464	1.9665	1.2171	0.8397
	Use phase	1.2426	2.6232	7.2524	2.6232	7.8696	2.6232
Marine eutrophication [kg N- eq]	Production	0.1262	0.0310	0.1242	0.1656	0.0751	0.0376
	Use phase	0.0199	0.0421	0.1163	0.0421	0.1262	0.0421
Metal depletion [kg Fe-eq]	Production	44.8012	11.5884	203.9456	30.0402	40.0138	5.5090
	Use phase	0.9639	2.0350	5.6261	2.0350	6.1050	2.0350
Natural land transformation [m2]	Production	0.0053	0.0041	0.0167	0.0149	0.0091	0.0052
	Use phase	0.0005	0.0011	0.0032	0.0011	0.0034	0.0011
Ozone depletion [kg CFC-11-eq]	Production	0.0001	0.0002	0.0000	0.0000	0.0002	0.0000
	Use phase	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Particulate matter formation [kg PM10-eq]	Production	0.1649	0.0719	0.3202	0.2174	0.2254	0.1376
	Use phase	0.0293	0.0618	0.1708	0.0618	0.1854	0.0618
Photochemical oxidant formation [kg NMVOC]	Production	0.1482	0.0847	0.3383	0.3185	0.2627	0.1468
	Use phase	0.0393	0.0829	0.2293	0.0829	0.2488	0.0829
Terrestrial acidification [kg SO2-eq]	Production	0.5708	0.1921	0.9766	0.5196	0.7061	0.1858
	Use phase	0.1376	0.2905	0.8032	0.2905	0.8715	0.2905
Terrestrial ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	0.0065	0.0058	0.0171	0.0089	0.0257	0.0033
	Use phase	0.0007	0.0016	0.0043	0.0016	0.0047	0.0016

Urban land occupation [m2a]	Production	0.5698	0.5400	1.3250	0.8337	0.5004	0.4449
	Use phase	0.0939	0.1983	0.5482	0.1983	0.5948	0.1983
Water depletion [m3]	Production	0.9668	1.1299	0.5093	0.7178	0.1592	0.1556
	Use phase	0.0882	0.1862	0.5147	0.1862	0.5585	0.1862
Abiotic depletion potential [kg Sb-eq]	Production	0.0319	0.0217	0.6983	0.0192	0.0038	0.0191
	Use phase	0.0008	0.0017	0.0047	0.0017	0.0051	0.0017

Table S4: Life cycle impacts per MWh in the 'T&D investment deferral' application.

		LIB-NMC	LIB-LFP	VRLA	LiS	VRFB	MgS-Evo2
Cumulative energy demand [MJ]	Production	928.7	1079.3	1154.1	2559.2	2201.5	761.5
	Use phase	430.5	908.8	2512.5	908.8	2726.3	908.8
Agricultural land occupation [m2a]	Production	4.2985	4.8735	7.6323	9.5486	4.2679	2.5171
	Use phase	0.0104	0.0220	0.0608	0.0220	0.0660	0.0220
Climate change [kg CO2-eq]	Production	57.8655	76.9591	71.1225	112.2320	150.0804	46.7536
	Use phase	24.1580	51.0002	141.0006	51.0002	153.0007	51.0002
Fossil depletion [kg oil-eq]	Production	15.6720	18.4780	20.8560	43.1478	47.9353	13.9565
	Use phase	7.3174	15.4478	42.7086	15.4478	46.3433	15.4478
Freshwater ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	2.3675	2.8927	5.6966	2.0618	3.0919	0.9183
	Use phase	1.3912	2.9369	8.1197	2.9369	8.8108	2.9369
Freshwater eutrophication [kg P-eq]	Production	0.0662	0.1072	0.1886	0.0825	0.0863	0.0301
	Use phase	0.0245	0.0518	0.1432	0.0518	0.1554	0.0518
Human toxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	100.2916	158.7647	396.8355	73.3244	311.2069	32.2935
	Use phase	17.5167	36.9797	102.2379	36.9797	110.9390	36.9797
Ionising radiation [kg U235-eq]	Production	10.6573	12.1200	8.1944	29.8696	8.3715	6.9973
	Use phase	0.6047	1.2766	3.5295	1.2766	3.8299	1.2766
Marine ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	2.3826	2.9795	5.9464	1.9665	3.2692	0.8797
	Use phase	1.2426	2.6232	7.2524	2.6232	7.8696	2.6232
Marine eutrophication [kg N-eq]	Production	0.2034	0.0749	0.1242	0.1656	0.2018	0.0394
	Use phase	0.0199	0.0421	0.1163	0.0421	0.1262	0.0421
Metal depletion [kg Fe-eq]	Production	72.2017	28.0140	203.9456	30.0402	107.4772	5.7709
	Use phase	0.9639	2.0350	5.6261	2.0350	6.1050	2.0350
Natural land transformation [m2]	Production	0.0085	0.0100	0.0167	0.0149	0.0245	0.0055
	Use phase	0.0005	0.0011	0.0032	0.0011	0.0034	0.0011
Ozone depletion [kg CFC-11-eq]	Production	0.0002	0.0006	0.0000	0.0000	0.0005	0.0000
	Use phase	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Particulate matter formation [kg PM10-eq]	Production	0.2658	0.1739	0.3202	0.2174	0.6054	0.1442
	Use phase	0.0293	0.0618	0.1708	0.0618	0.1854	0.0618
Photochemical oxidant formation [kg NMVOC]	Production	0.2388	0.2047	0.3383	0.3185	0.7057	0.1538
	Use phase	0.0393	0.0829	0.2293	0.0829	0.2488	0.0829
Terrestrial acidification [kg SO2-eq]	Production	0.9199	0.4643	0.9766	0.5196	1.8967	0.1947
	Use phase	0.1376	0.2905	0.8032	0.2905	0.8715	0.2905
Terrestrial ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	0.0105	0.0140	0.0171	0.0089	0.0691	0.0035
	Use phase	0.0007	0.0016	0.0043	0.0016	0.0047	0.0016
Urban land occupation [m2a]	Production	0.9184	1.3053	1.3250	0.8337	1.3441	0.4661
	Use phase	0.0939	0.1983	0.5482	0.1983	0.5948	0.1983

Water depletion [m ³]	Production	1.5582	2.7315	0.5093	0.7178	0.4277	0.1630
	Use phase	0.0882	0.1862	0.5147	0.1862	0.5585	0.1862
Abiotic depletion potential [kg Sb-eq]	Production	0.0515	0.0523	0.6983	0.0192	0.0103	0.0200
	Use phase	0.0008	0.0017	0.0047	0.0017	0.0051	0.0017

Table S5: Life cycle impacts per MWh in the 'utility energy time-shift' application.

	Battery type	LIB-NMC	LIB-LFP	VRLA	LiS	VRFB	MgS- Evo2
Cumulative energy demand [MJ]	Production	631.5	733.9	1154.1	2559.2	1497.0	726.9
	Use phase	430.5	908.8	2512.5	908.8	2726.3	908.8
Agricultural land occupation [m ² a]	Production	2.9230	3.3140	7.6323	9.5486	2.9022	2.4029
	Use phase	0.0104	0.0220	0.0608	0.0220	0.0660	0.0220
Climate change [kg CO ₂ -eq]	Production	39.3485	52.3322	71.1225	112.2320	102.0547	44.6317
	Use phase	24.1580	51.0002	141.0006	51.0002	153.0007	51.0002
Fossil depletion [kg oil-eq]	Production	10.6569	12.5650	20.8560	43.1478	32.5960	13.3230
	Use phase	7.3174	15.4478	42.7086	15.4478	46.3433	15.4478
Freshwater ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	1.6099	1.9670	5.6966	2.0618	2.1025	0.8767
	Use phase	1.3912	2.9369	8.1197	2.9369	8.8108	2.9369
Freshwater eutrophication [kg P-eq]	Production	0.0450	0.0729	0.1886	0.0825	0.0587	0.0288
	Use phase	0.0245	0.0518	0.1432	0.0518	0.1554	0.0518
Human toxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	68.1983	107.9600	396.8355	73.3244	211.6207	30.8278
	Use phase	17.5167	36.9797	102.2379	36.9797	110.9390	36.9797
Ionising radiation [kg U ₂₃₅ -eq]	Production	7.2470	8.2416	8.1944	29.8696	5.6926	6.6797
	Use phase	0.6047	1.2766	3.5295	1.2766	3.8299	1.2766
Marine ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	1.6202	2.0261	5.9464	1.9665	2.2230	0.8397
	Use phase	1.2426	2.6232	7.2524	2.6232	7.8696	2.6232
Marine eutrophication [kg N-eq]	Production	0.1383	0.0510	0.1242	0.1656	0.1372	0.0376
	Use phase	0.0199	0.0421	0.1163	0.0421	0.1262	0.0421
Metal depletion [kg Fe-eq]	Production	49.0972	19.0495	203.9456	30.0402	73.0845	5.5090
	Use phase	0.9639	2.0350	5.6261	2.0350	6.1050	2.0350
Natural land transformation [m ²]	Production	0.0058	0.0068	0.0167	0.0149	0.0166	0.0052
	Use phase	0.0005	0.0011	0.0032	0.0011	0.0034	0.0011
Ozone depletion [kg CFC-11-eq]	Production	0.0002	0.0004	0.0000	0.0000	0.0004	0.0000
	Use phase	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Particulate matter formation [kg PM ₁₀ -eq]	Production	0.1807	0.1183	0.3202	0.2174	0.4117	0.1376
	Use phase	0.0293	0.0618	0.1708	0.0618	0.1854	0.0618
Photochemical oxidant formation [kg NMVOC]	Production	0.1624	0.1392	0.3383	0.3185	0.4799	0.1468
	Use phase	0.0393	0.0829	0.2293	0.0829	0.2488	0.0829
Terrestrial acidification [kg SO ₂ -eq]	Production	0.6255	0.3157	0.9766	0.5196	1.2898	0.1858
	Use phase	0.1376	0.2905	0.8032	0.2905	0.8715	0.2905
Terrestrial ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	0.0071	0.0095	0.0171	0.0089	0.0470	0.0033
	Use phase	0.0007	0.0016	0.0043	0.0016	0.0047	0.0016
Urban land occupation [m ² a]	Production	0.6245	0.8876	1.3250	0.8337	0.9140	0.4449
	Use phase	0.0939	0.1983	0.5482	0.1983	0.5948	0.1983
Water depletion [m ³]	Production	1.0595	1.8574	0.5093	0.7178	0.2908	0.1556
	Use phase	0.0882	0.1862	0.5147	0.1862	0.5585	0.1862

Abiotic depletion potential [kg Sb-eq]	Production	0.0350	0.0356	0.6983	0.0192	0.0070	0.0191
	Use phase	0.0008	0.0017	0.0047	0.0017	0.0051	0.0017

Table S6: Life cycle impacts per MWh in the 'support of voltage regulation' application.

		LIB-NMC	LIB-LFP	VRLA	LiS	VRFB	MgS- Evo2
Cumulative energy demand [MJ]	Production	928.7	1079.3	1154.1	2559.2	2201.5	761.5
	Use phase	430.5	908.8	2512.5	908.8	2726.3	908.8
Agricultural land occupation [m2a]	Production	4.2985	4.8735	7.6323	9.5486	4.2679	2.5171
	Use phase	0.0104	0.0220	0.0608	0.0220	0.0660	0.0220
Climate change [kg CO2-eq]	Production	57.8655	76.9591	71.1225	112.2320	150.0804	46.7536
	Use phase	24.1580	51.0002	141.0006	51.0002	153.0007	51.0002
Fossil depletion [kg oil-eq]	Production	15.6720	18.4780	20.8560	43.1478	47.9353	13.9565
	Use phase	7.3174	15.4478	42.7086	15.4478	46.3433	15.4478
Freshwater ecotoxicity [kg 1,4- DCB-eq]	Production	2.3675	2.8927	5.6966	2.0618	3.0919	0.9183
	Use phase	1.3912	2.9369	8.1197	2.9369	8.8108	2.9369
Freshwater eutrophication [kg P-eq]	Production	0.0662	0.1072	0.1886	0.0825	0.0863	0.0301
	Use phase	0.0245	0.0518	0.1432	0.0518	0.1554	0.0518
Human toxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	100.2916	158.7647	396.8355	73.3244	311.2069	32.2935
	Use phase	17.5167	36.9797	102.2379	36.9797	110.9390	36.9797
Ionising radiation [kg U235-eq]	Production	10.6573	12.1200	8.1944	29.8696	8.3715	6.9973
	Use phase	0.6047	1.2766	3.5295	1.2766	3.8299	1.2766
Marine ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	2.3826	2.9795	5.9464	1.9665	3.2692	0.8797
	Use phase	1.2426	2.6232	7.2524	2.6232	7.8696	2.6232
Marine eutrophication [kg N- eq]	Production	0.2034	0.0749	0.1242	0.1656	0.2018	0.0394
	Use phase	0.0199	0.0421	0.1163	0.0421	0.1262	0.0421
Metal depletion [kg Fe-eq]	Production	72.2017	28.0140	203.9456	30.0402	107.4772	5.7709
	Use phase	0.9639	2.0350	5.6261	2.0350	6.1050	2.0350
Natural land transformation [m2]	Production	0.0085	0.0100	0.0167	0.0149	0.0245	0.0055
	Use phase	0.0005	0.0011	0.0032	0.0011	0.0034	0.0011
Ozone depletion [kg CFC-11-eq]	Production	0.0002	0.0006	0.0000	0.0000	0.0005	0.0000
	Use phase	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Particulate matter formation [kg PM10-eq]	Production	0.2658	0.1739	0.3202	0.2174	0.6054	0.1442
	Use phase	0.0293	0.0618	0.1708	0.0618	0.1854	0.0618
Photochemical oxidant formation [kg NMVOC]	Production	0.2388	0.2047	0.3383	0.3185	0.7057	0.1538
	Use phase	0.0393	0.0829	0.2293	0.0829	0.2488	0.0829
Terrestrial acidification [kg SO2-eq]	Production	0.9199	0.4643	0.9766	0.5196	1.8967	0.1947
	Use phase	0.1376	0.2905	0.8032	0.2905	0.8715	0.2905
Terrestrial ecotoxicity [kg 1,4- DCB-eq]	Production	0.0105	0.0140	0.0171	0.0089	0.0691	0.0035
	Use phase	0.0007	0.0016	0.0043	0.0016	0.0047	0.0016
Urban land occupation [m2a]	Production	0.9184	1.3053	1.3250	0.8337	1.3441	0.4661
	Use phase	0.0939	0.1983	0.5482	0.1983	0.5948	0.1983
Water depletion [m3]	Production	1.5582	2.7315	0.5093	0.7178	0.4277	0.1630
	Use phase	0.0882	0.1862	0.5147	0.1862	0.5585	0.1862
Abiotic depletion potential [kg Sb-eq]	Production	0.0515	0.0523	0.6983	0.0192	0.0103	0.0200
	Use phase	0.0008	0.0017	0.0047	0.0017	0.0051	0.0017

Table S7: Life cycle impacts per MWh in the 'renewables support' application.

		LIB-NMC	LIB-LFP	VRLA	LiS	VRFB	MgS-Evo2
Cumulative energy demand [MJ]	Production	576.24	655.27	1154.15	2559.21	1336.62	726.94
	Use phase	246.54	520.47	1438.94	520.47	1561.40	520.47
Agricultural land occupation [m2a]	Production	2.6672	2.9589	7.6323	9.5486	2.5912	2.4029
	Use phase	0.0008	0.0016	0.0045	0.0016	0.0049	0.0016
Climate change [kg CO2-eq]	Production	35.9056	46.7252	71.1225	112.2320	91.1203	44.6317
	Use phase	2.7199	5.7420	15.8750	5.7420	17.2261	5.7420
Fossil depletion [kg oil-eq]	Production	9.7245	11.2188	20.8560	43.1478	29.1036	13.3230
	Use phase	0.8105	1.7110	4.7305	1.7110	5.1331	1.7110
Freshwater ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	1.4691	1.7563	5.6966	2.0618	1.8772	0.8767
	Use phase	0.5890	1.2434	3.4376	1.2434	3.7302	1.2434
Freshwater eutrophication [kg P-eq]	Production	0.0411	0.0651	0.1886	0.0825	0.0524	0.0288
	Use phase	0.0023	0.0048	0.0133	0.0048	0.0145	0.0048
Human toxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	62.2309	96.3928	396.8355	73.3244	188.9470	30.8278
	Use phase	3.9003	8.2339	22.7644	8.2339	24.7018	8.2339
Ionising radiation [kg U235-eq]	Production	6.6129	7.3586	8.1944	29.8696	5.0827	6.6797
	Use phase	0.2284	0.4821	1.3329	0.4821	1.4463	0.4821
Marine ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	1.4784	1.8090	5.9464	1.9665	1.9848	0.8397
	Use phase	0.5228	1.1037	3.0513	1.1037	3.3110	1.1037
Marine eutrophication [kg N-eq]	Production	0.1262	0.0455	0.1242	0.1656	0.1225	0.0376
	Use phase	0.0036	0.0075	0.0208	0.0075	0.0225	0.0075
Metal depletion [kg Fe-eq]	Production	44.8012	17.0085	203.9456	30.0402	65.2540	5.5090
	Use phase	1.1803	2.4917	6.8888	2.4917	7.4751	2.4917
Natural land transformation [m2]	Production	0.0053	0.0061	0.0167	0.0149	0.0149	0.0052
	Use phase	0.0001	0.0003	0.0007	0.0003	0.0008	0.0003
Ozone depletion [kg CFC-11-eq]	Production	0.0001	0.0003	0.0000	0.0000	0.0003	0.0000
	Use phase	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Particulate matter formation [kg PM10-eq]	Production	0.1649	0.1056	0.3202	0.2174	0.3676	0.1376
	Use phase	0.0071	0.0150	0.0415	0.0150	0.0450	0.0150
Photochemical oxidant formation [kg NMVOC]	Production	0.1482	0.1243	0.3383	0.3185	0.4285	0.1468
	Use phase	0.0107	0.0225	0.0623	0.0225	0.0676	0.0225
Terrestrial acidification [kg SO2-eq]	Production	0.5708	0.2819	0.9766	0.5196	1.1516	0.1858
	Use phase	0.0152	0.0320	0.0884	0.0320	0.0960	0.0320
Terrestrial ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DCB-eq]	Production	0.0065	0.0085	0.0171	0.0089	0.0419	0.0033
	Use phase	0.0004	0.0009	0.0025	0.0009	0.0027	0.0009
Urban land occupation [m2a]	Production	0.5698	0.7925	1.3250	0.8337	0.8161	0.4449
	Use phase	0.0461	0.0974	0.2692	0.0974	0.2921	0.0974
Water depletion [m3]	Production	0.9668	1.6584	0.5093	0.7178	0.2597	0.1556
	Use phase	0.0122	0.0258	0.0714	0.0258	0.0774	0.0258
Abiotic depletion potential [kg Sb-eq]	Production	0.0319	0.0318	0.6983	0.0192	0.0063	0.0191
	Use phase	0.0017	0.0036	0.0100	0.0036	0.0109	0.0036